

INTELLECTUAL AND IMMATERIAL BANK

<https://intellectualandimmaterialbank.com>

BY WISE JESTER

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August 2021, Oslo, Norway

What is IIB?

The Intellectual and Immaterial Bank (or IIB) by Wise Jester is a blind, kind, humor-based, algorithmically assisted network for intellectual inclusion, neurodiversity, and hybrid-knowledge professions.

To be specific, IIB is:

Blind, because *he* does not require, neither process any data that “facially” describe you: no photos, no names, no gender, no ethnicity, no age.

Humor-based, because the core IIB services are based on Humor Science and the Science of Complex Systems, with experimental evidence.

Algorithmically assisted, because – due to his blindness – IIB delivers such results that are both intellectually compatible and challenging for the receivers at both ends of a connection – in a unique, for them, harmony.

Intellectual inclusion and neurodiversity are key to the quality of hybrid professions in the transforming society. And this is IIB’s main mission.

IIB facilitates emergence of collaborations with **shared visions**, equipped with **hybrid knowledge**, **imagination and other qualities quantified**, where the users can also add their **improvisations** in the blind system, so that other users may read it and decide if their vision is shared.

Symmetry in IIB guarantees that the initiative to connect can come from either side: collaborations or individuals. Considering that every request implies making a choice of 5 knowledge areas and provides the requested with at least 3, plus a few surprising options, IIB practically facilitates the emergence of hybrid-knowledge professions – in neurodiversity, to round this up.

WARNING: IIB contains sarcasm and irony!

you just go through a peaceful humor session in no-exam

– Open up! It's the police!
– How did you get yourself in there?

12/36

You own your data. You get a punk "mohawk" of your intellectual uniqueness, which is your only picture that other users can "see". You use your mohawk to build up your de facto collaborations or to attract those. IIB is a blind gamified network. The last say between you and others will have a shared vision.

[BEGIN AS AN INDEPENDENT PROFESSIONAL](#)

[BEGIN AS AN AUTHOR OF A COLLABORATION](#)

you just go through a peaceful humor session in no-exam

- Oh, dear, you're all wet! Take off your clothes, I'll bring you something dry.
- Thanks!
- Here you go, this is the 2010 Croix aux Moines Chardonnay.

32/36

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[BEGIN AS AN INDEPENDENT PROFESSIONAL](#)

[BEGIN AS AN AUTHOR OF A COLLABORATION](#)

WARNING: high content of irony and sarcasm!

**IIB is playful. The contents of his jokes are not made to conclude about you or your context!
He is a complex mathematical system of patterns.**

Our opponents take advantage of the fact that they're smarter. That's not fair!

31/36

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BEGIN AS AN INDEPENDENT PROFESSIONAL

And, completely blind.

BEGIN AS AN AUTHOR OF A COLLABORATION

And, please, do not treat the jokes of IIB as advice! :)

If lost in the woods, begin talking about politics. Sure, someone will appear to argue.

29/36

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BEGIN AS AN INDEPENDENT PROFESSIONAL

**IIB is a computational
change agent**

BEGIN AS AN AUTHOR OF A COLLABORATION

Why “Wise Jester”?

As we know, in the Middle Ages, it was uncommon to criticize king, and king had to be careful with criticizing his influential network. Usually, the brightest people at the court, jesters, were a sort of “communication” means. Sometimes, a domestic jester was perceived as the king’s reflection.

Therefore, jesters enjoyed immunity against prosecution.

(Simon Newman, “Jesters in the Middle Ages”)

IIB online:

<https://intellectualandimmaterialbank.com>

Indications for use of IIB

biased, subjective judgment of intellectual variety

need of intellectual diversity and harmony in high-risk innovation processes

conformism in professional contexts, leading to bureaucracy, closed mindset and lost visions

failures in change processes and inclusion programs, where intellectual diversity is confused with “quota”

lack of measurement of transitional thinking from the known to the unknown in no-exam situations

lack of tracing the emergence of hybrid professions with respective intellectual flexibility

MORE about the problems IN NUMBERS: see presentation <https://zenodo.org/record/5171424>

PS: IIB is implemented to serve and complete this mission!

What does the new economic reality demand and need?

“Hybrid roles are growing at twice the rate [...] and are 20-40% higher-paying than their more traditional counterparts.” ♠

“Hybrid jobs draw upon skill sets from widely different, traditionally unrelated fields. They’re complex, multidisciplinary, and often blend technical left-brain skills with creative right-brain skills”. ♠

“Jobs are mutating to be unexpected”, what requires cracking “the secret of career success in the digital world ahead.” ♠

“Hybrid jobs are significantly more likely to demand skills like writing, creativity, and collaboration than jobs in general. [...] Just like the marketing manager who is now an analyst, the software engineer or data scientist is now a business person, designer, and team worker.” ♦

♠ edX Blog, edX Team, Hybrid Jobs: A 4-Minute Primer on Fast-Growing, Lucrative Career Paths (2020)

♦ Burning Glass Technologies, The Hybrid Job Economy: How New Skills are Rewriting the DNA of the Job Market (2019)

Anna Andreyevna
12 October 2016 · 🌐

ME AFTER A WORKSHOP ABOUT EMERGING PROFESSIONS AT THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

What a highly useful and promising meeting (and two more) at the European Commission! 😊 Asteroid miner, professional gamer, space clinician, image consultant, civilian drone controller, exobiologist, etc. 😊 The degree of my joy is immeasurable – I can't stop smiling 😊 being very serious 😊

Gianni Tee, Robert Booker and 4 others

1 comment

Like

Comment

Share

Brent Schneeman

1

Like · Reply · 4 y

Write a comment...

UN Global Compact Norway

3,594 followers

Promoted

Unicus ansetter kun mennesker med Asperger. Statnett mener kompetansen er vanskelig å få tak i, og kan bidra til å spare Statnett for flerfoldige millioner. Hør hvordan Unicus mener at asperger er et konkurransefortrinn som krever lite tilrettelegging.

Faglig påfyll

Asperger som konkurransefortrinn

FN FREMTIDENS NÆRINGSLIV

Asperger som konkurransefortrinn

fremtidensnaringsliv.no

[Learn more](#)

How the indicated problems have been approached in the new socio-economic reality?

Conventionally, top-down, mainly in organizational interests: HR

In no “facial” data disclosure, bottom-up, mainly for interest-based community-building: Reddit, Telegram, Signal, Discord

For economic empowerment of independent professionals, bottom-up: Upwork, Fiverr, Toptal, Freelancer.com, Insolve

As an emerging phenomenon of neurodiverse companies: Unicus

IIB does much more and with an emerging effect where $2+2=5$ [X]

IIB is blind, showing uniqueness of deeper and autopilot thinking [+ more] in professionals, and needs in it at collaborations, in mutual compatibility and challenge, with at least 3 out of 5 knowledge areas, where shared visions have the last say

Your capacities

Your strongest capacity for making change is proposing idiotic ideas, which will be right soon.

While thinking, you are rather after imagination. You tend to react immediately to social signals. You prefer working in low-pressure contexts.

- preferred comfort zones
 - Low-pressure contexts
 - Contexts with high uncertainty
 - Collectivistic environments
 - High-pressure contexts
 - Independent genre
- Instant-th. triggers
 - Social signals
 - Cognitive signals
 - Emotional signals
 - Knowledge
 - Focused aim
- deep-th. triggers
 - Solidarity with others
 - Imagination
 - Coming up with alternatives
- capacities for transformation
 - Faster taking the new into practice
 - Having a discovery mindset, capable of synthesis
 - Proposing idiotic ideas, which will be right soon
 - Breaking old things down faster
 - Standing for flat collaboration of hybrid competencies

Needs of your collaboration

Your collaboration may have a challenge with structures and processes that are stuck.

Your collaboration may experience ignoring uniqueness. Your collaboration might be overlooking how others feel. Your collaboration disrupts comfort zones by expecting individual initiative.

- disruption of comfort
 - Pressuring the members
 - Demanding clarity and plan
 - Expecting individual initiative
 - Slowing down for well-ordered actions
 - Accountability and transparency
- tendency to ignore
 - The socially accepted
 - Facts and numbers
 - How others feel
 - Siloed thinking
 - Being too dispersed
- Intellectual depth
 - Ignoring uniqueness
 - Being too down-to-earth
 - Structures and processes that are stuck
- needs in transformation
 - Fear of deviation
 - Seeing the big picture
 - Obvious needs in new, unknown ideas
 - Degree of inner passion of the members
 - Potential for synergic collaboration

WARNING: for nerds only!

What can the humor module of IIB do?

In IIB, humor appreciation provides data generation, computed to show you your own unique way of thinking when contexts collide. IIB patternizes the course of your thinking in transition from the known to the unknown when you discover that seemingly unrelated contexts do, actually, relate. Variants of them in IIB are infinite, and your unique, honest grading of jokes provides you with your own, unique results. Properly argued and anchored in Humor Science, the module shows you your instinctive (unconscious, autopilot) thinking and deeper (conscious aware) thinking, beautifully theorized by Daniel Kahneman, who got a Nobel prize in behavioral economics for that. The theory was further developed by a humor scientist Larry Ventis, and his peers in Cognitive Science, Linguistics, Psychology, Behaviorism, and more. Also, that theory was accurately applied by Jon Ivar Johansen to explore change processes in organizations, starting from individuals. Compiled in a unique way with practice, the elements of the accumulated knowledge emerged into a synthesized, relationship-intensive module in IIB, full of mathematical calculations, created and applied by the founder of Wise Jester with background in science and a bunch of other knowledge & practice areas. Mathematically and computationally, IIB considers the tendency of human mind to equilibrium and, also, values its natural “edge of chaos”, including such features as imagination and spontaneity.

A permanent link to a document with some relevant science extracts:
<https://zenodo.org/record/4724974>

What does IIB return?

USERS of IIB: persons with professional interests

each person sees an own bouquet of intellectual patterns to apply when contexts collide

Your strongest capacity for making change is having a discovery mindset, capable of synthesis.

While thinking, you are rather after imagination.
 You tend to react immediately to cognitive signals.
 You prefer working in independent genre.

**Complex Systems, Hybrid Innovation, Entrepreneurship,
 Social Work, Music**

preferred comfort zones
 Instant-th. triggers
 deep-th. triggers
 capacities for transformation

- Low-pressure contexts
- Contexts with high uncertainty
- Collectivistic environments
- High-pressure contexts
- Independent genre
- Social signals
- Cognitive signals
- Emotional signals
- Knowledge
- Focused aim
- Solidarity with others
- Imagination
- Coming up with alternatives
- Faster taking the new into practice
- Having a discovery mindset, capable of synthesis
- Proposing idiotic ideas, which will be right soon
- Breaking old things down faster
- Standing for flat collaboration of hybrid competencies

how you thought things to take course

BOOM!
 he-he, new data

What would you do?
 How?
 Why?

You can initiate your professional, visionary collaboration on your terms!

among all who are available for you to be discovered

Your strongest capacity for making change is **proposing idiotic ideas, which will be right soon.**
 While thinking, you are rather after **imagination.**
 You tend to react immediately to **social signals.**
 You prefer working in **low-pressure contexts.**

Pitched:

I am a dreamer and doer who wants to build intelligence-intensive mechatronic solutions of tomorrow.

and you "look" for others
 ...like this person

or this person

or this one

...computationally assisted...

Username: dshwi363kshkytq65w33sd2kshu289hksqmbg891hjkshqlqqk
 This person is favorably complementing you in response to new situations by being rather sensitive to **emotional signals.**
 While thinking before doing, this person also goes for **focused aim.**
 The main strength of this person is in **having a discovery mindset, capable of synthesis.**
 The competencies, which this person shares with your request, are primarily: **engineering, entrepreneurship, gaming, statistics.**
 The unique competencies, which this person can bring in, are: **physics.**
Pitched: I am crazy about math and physics, because we can make even more new solutions if we better understand Mother Nature!

to compile a collaboration with you

Username: sjaqpqkgjagd652o1hwekhsjgkah82o2tyuq2jgdqhgwhfjkjh
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 The unique competencies, which this person can bring in, are: **physics, robotics.**
Pitched: My main interest is emerging business models, and I would love to join a startup that works on a highly unique idea.

Username: qjgksjdjahgdw82632jgahfwhqjt2i1gsgdj1tidbj2tksvghj187ejs
 This person is favorably complementing you in response to new situations by being rather sensitive to **cognitive signals.**
 While thinking before doing, this person also goes for **focused aim.**
 The main strength of this person is in **breaking old things down faster.**
 The competencies, which this person shares with your request, are primarily: **math, engineering.**
 The unique competencies, which this person can bring in, are: **complex systems, robotics, coding.**
Pitched: Robots are my everything. I worked in industrial robotics, and now I want to build a humanoid of my own.

[Print-screened from IIB + feature update from June 22, 2021.]

You are available for them just like they are available for you to be seen and contacted!

This is you

Your strongest capacity for making change is **proposing idiotic ideas, which will be right soon.**
 While thinking, you are rather after **imagination.**
 You tend to react immediately to **social signals.**
 You prefer working in **low-pressure contexts.**

Pitched:

I am a dreamer and doer who wants to build intelligence-intensive mechatronic solutions of tomorrow.

and you "look" for others
 ...like this person

or this person

or this one

...computationally assisted...

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

among all who are available for you to be discovered

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 Pitched: My main interest is emerging business models, and I would love to join a startup that works on a highly unique idea.

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

with a shared dream or vision

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 Pitched: Robots are my everything. I worked in industrial robotics, and now I want to build a humanoid of my own.

[Print-screened from IIB + feature update from June 22, 2021]

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

The ends of a connection are not only mutually harmonious to each other in their deeper thinking and the perception of comfort, but the requesting one receives at least 3 out of 5 knowledge areas requested, if those are available, with the 1st as obligatory. With a few surprises! Because IIB keeps you open to the options.

This is you

and you "look" for others
...like this person

or this person

or this one

...computationally assisted...

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INTRODUCE YOURSELF

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to compile a collaboration with you

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Pitched: My main interest is emerging business models, and I would love to join a startup that works on a highly unique idea.

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

with hybrid knowledge

Username: qjgksjdjahgdw82632jgahfwhqjt2i1gsgdj1tidbj2tksvghj187ejs
This person is favorably complementing you in response to new situations by being rather sensitive to **cognitive signals.**
While thinking before doing, this person also goes for **focused aim.**
The main strength of this person is in **breaking old things down faster.**
The competencies, which this person shares with your request, are primarily: **math, engineering.**
The unique competencies, which this person can bring in, are: **complex systems, robotics, coding.**
Pitched: Robots are my everything. I worked in industrial robotics, and now I want to build a humanoid of my own.

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

[Print-screened from IIB + feature update from June 22, 2021]

Hybrid-knowledge choice selection

What are the domains of your professional interests formal and informal? Choose 5.
You can select what have you studied, worked with and are curios of, and what you simply love.

Physics Engineering Statistics Math XR Robotics Coding Regulation
Economics Gaming Entrepreneurship User experience Social work Writing
Music Complex systems Hybrid innovation Communication Arts Sports
Medicine Blockchain Environment Audiovisual works Design Art

DONE!

**which can always
be enriched for
you at your
request**

You own your data. You get a punk "mohawk" of your intellectual uniqueness, which is your only picture that other users can "see". You use your mohawk to build up your de facto collaborations or to attract those. IIB is a blind gamified network. The last say between you and others will have a shared vision.

BEGIN AS AN INDEPENDENT PROFESSIONAL

BEGIN AS AN AUTHOR OF A COLLABORATION

What does IIB return?

USERS: collaborations of professionals

your collaboration acts as a bouquet of needs when contexts collide, looking for hybrid knowledge, and the vision shared

- | | |
|-------------------------|---|
| disruption of comfort | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Pressuring the members ■ Demanding clarity and plan ■ Expecting individual initiative ■ Slowing down for well-ordered actions ■ Accountability and transparency |
| tendency to ignore | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ The socially accepted ■ Facts and numbers ■ How others feel ■ Siloed thinking ■ Being too dispersed ■ Ignoring uniqueness ■ Being too down-to-earth |
| Intellectual depth | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Structures and processes that are stuck ■ Fear of deviation ■ Seeing the big picture ■ Obvious needs in new, unknown ideas ■ Degree of inner passion of the members ■ Potential for synergic collaboration |
| needs in transformation | |

Your collaboration is not pictured as a trendy name, big tokens, or well-dressed C[X]Os with wide smiles – because you should not be marginalizing yourself from immaterial exchange and the free flow of intelligence.

Needs of your collaboration

IIB will be honest with you, but nobody else will see that this is you!

Because IIB is blind like a bat, and he makes all his users blind too – to see further and better.

Your collaboration may have a challenge with fear of deviation.

Your collaboration may experience ignoring uniqueness. Your collaboration might be overlooking how others feel. Your collaboration disrupts comfort zones by expecting individual initiative.

you as a collaboration act like an attractor,

DEMAND for SUPPLY

+

-

Needs of my collaboration

and you "look" for others
...like this person

or this person

or this one

...computationally
assisted...

Your collaboration may have a challenge with structures and processes that are stuck.

Your collaboration may experience being too dispersed.

Your collaboration might be overlooking the socially accepted.

Your collaboration disrupts comfort zones by pressuring the members.

Pitched:

Our team is looking for a bright developer who understands the social complexity around emerging technologies and can work fast.

Are you aware of Physics? You are a "plus".

...among them all

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

Username: jwgejay2731kjqhwmmai2u01lkqajy2g1jhhqf62reamo03egh120

The strongest capacity of this person for making change is faster taking the new into practice.

To balance your work style, this person prefers working in collectivistic environments.

When thinking over something in depth, this person goes for solidarity with others.

The competencies of this person, which you requested for your collaboration, are primarily: coding, robotics.

The unique competencies, which this person can bring into your collaboration, are: statistics, physics, engineering.

Pitched: I am a Java developer, and I am available to become a part of a new environment. I love travelling too.

to strengthen up the collaboration

Username: sjghwja721klwka89q2kajwhdjba827jhwekq3ryhjfqh62jq2g

The strongest capacity of this person for making change is proposing idiotic ideas, which will be right soon.

To balance your work style, this person prefers working in high-pressure contexts.

When thinking over something in depth, this person goes for imagination.

The competencies of this person, which you requested for your collaboration, are primarily: xr, robotics.

The unique competencies, which this person can bring into your collaboration, are: complex systems, entrepreneurship, engineering.

Pitched: I am developing a new type of digital wallets. I am looking for collaborations that develop respective user applications.

with a shared dream or vision

Username: dshwi363kshkytq65w33sd2kshu289hksqmbg891hjkshqlqqk

The strongest capacity of this person for making change is breaking old things down faster.

To balance your work style, this person prefers working in contexts with high uncertainty.

When thinking over something in depth, this person goes for focused aim.

The competencies of this person, which you requested for your collaboration, are primarily: coding, robotics.

The unique competencies, which this person can bring into your collaboration, are: complex systems, math, engineering.

Pitched: My dream is to create machines that talk!

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

And they are "minuses".

Wise Jester

18

[Print-screened from IIB + feature update from June 22, 2021]

you as a collaboration act like an attractor,

DEMAND for SUPPLY

+

-

Needs of my collaboration

and you "look" for others
...like this person

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Your collaboration might be overlooking the socially accepted.

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Pitched:

Our team is looking for a bright developer who understands the social complexity around emerging technologies and can work fast.

...you are a "plus" ...

...among them all

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

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with hybrid knowledge

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

Username: dshwi363kshkytq65w33sd2kshu289hksqmbg891hjkshlqqk

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The competencies of this person, which you requested for your collaboration, are primarily: coding, robotics.

The unique competencies, which this person can bring into your collaboration, are: complex systems, math, engineering.

Pitched: My dream is to create machines that talk!

...and they are "minuses" ...

Wise Jester

IIB is a fair game. Not only collaborations can look for people, but people can look for collaborations.
SYMMETRY! Because why not?

...and they are “plusses”...

**TRY IT!
 AND INVITE
 MORE PEOPLE**

**MORE PEOPLE
 = MORE
 COLLABORATIONS**

Your strongest capacity for making change is **having a discovery mindset, capable of synthesis.**
 While thinking, you are rather after **imagination.**
 You tend to react immediately to **cognitive signals.**
 You prefer working in **independent genre.**

Pitched:

I am a maker of IIB, and I am looking for more bright and dedicated people to join me in this world

...you are a “minus” ...

Collaboration name: The Lorenz family
 The highest need in change of this collaboration is **obvious needs in new, unknown ideas.**
 What would be comfortable to you in this collaboration is **demanding clarity and plan.**
 This collaboration has an intellectual challenge in **being too down-to-earth.**
 The competencies, which this collaboration has for you, are: **robotics, math, entrepreneurship.**
 The unique competencies, which you can develop at this collaboration, are: **arts, hybrid innovation.**
Pitched: We are programmers who can simulate chaos for you or an egde of it. Tokenized. And we are looking for a lawyer.

Collaboration name: Experiment Stitch

The highest need in change of this collaboration is **fear of deviation.**
 What would be comfortable to you in this collaboration is **expecting individual initiative.**
 This collaboration has an intellectual challenge in **being too down-to-earth.**
 The competencies, which this collaboration has for you, are: **robotics, math, entrepreneurship.**
 The unique competencies, which you can develop at this collaboration, are: **arts, hybrid innovation.**
Pitched: Mechatronic animation for visualizations of dreams.

Collaboration name: Wonders of Emergence

The highest need in change of this collaboration is **obvious needs in new, unknown ideas.**
 What would be comfortable to you in this collaboration is **expecting individual initiative.**
 This collaboration has an intellectual challenge in **being too down-to-earth.**
 The competencies, which this collaboration has for you, are: **robotics, math, entrepreneurship.**
 The unique competencies, which you can develop at this collaboration, are: **arts, hybrid innovation.**
Pitched: 011235813213455891442333776109871597...

[Print-screened from IIB + feature update from August 12, 2021]

Wise Jester

Communication on IIB

Me contacting individuals [independent professionals]:

- On my behalf _____
- On behalf of my collaboration _____

Me contacting collaborations

Me being contacted:

- By other individuals [independent professionals]
- By collaborations

Conversations in my collaborations

My everybody

What can that give to you? That is the fun part: surprises.

But! You must be a person of integrity and respect other people. Don't steal, don't cheat. Behave decent.

I regularly update the General Instruction and News.

Visual explanation of the – already – implemented IIB

USERS: collaborations of independent professionals

For every request, IIB compiles at least 3 out of 5 knowledge areas, with the 1st area in the request as obligatory, plus shows unique options, out of the request, from the receivers' choices of knowledge areas – for every computationally assisted connection in deeper and instant thinking, computed from individual humor appreciation when contexts collide.

combinations of domain knowledge into hybrid, approved individually by selection and vision-based, informed choice making, in no social pressure on the individuals, acting in harmonious collaborations, compiled in intellectual compatibility and challenge

emergence of new industries
 from more projects solving difficult problems
 minimizing the gap between conventional industries and emerging technologies
 with intellectual inclusion and neurodiversity

having fun

+ and/or any of your friends and colleagues by invitation

Expected impact of IIB

Larger number of organically self-organizing hybrid-knowledge initiatives: by 75%

Raise in the number of emerging technologies: by 65%, considering the social inertia

Increase in the capacity of risk taking by people: max 35% of people can accept risk, and IIB may enlarge that up to 70%

Emergence of more conscious collaborations with solid, honestly shared visions: 60% of growth in this will be a success

Disruption of mediators : 0% of HR involvement is required

And that is targeting the international level.

IIB is in English and uses the principles of humor universality deduced in Humor Science. Most of the jokes in IIB are originally Russian as of now, but the Norwegian UX participants say “The humor was too American...”

I am glad. Very glad. Bond, James Bond. Damme, Van Damme, Claude Van Damme, Jean-Claude Van Damme.

TEAM Wise Jester

The founder of Wise Jester, born 2019, **Anna Zaytseva**, born 1987, has been working on the IIB concept for 11 years. I received a PhD in **Management of Information Systems** for that purpose and worked with content development at an innovation-support center for social welfare solutions in South Norway. I am building IIB as a **Complex System**. I have a certificate from the **Complex Systems Summer School** at the Santa Fe Institute, a master's degree in **International and European Relations** and an honors specialist degree in **Jurisprudence**. I am the brain and engine of the IIB development.

The web developer **Alexey Egoshin** holds a PhD in **Mathematical Modelling**, a patent in **chaos simulation**, more than 12 years of experience in **web engineering**, and a portfolio of **collaborative projects** with companies from the USA, Europe, Canada and Israel. The projects include a web platform for optimizing recruitment and branding, game strategies, and a web platform for trading on financial markets. He has been working with me on IIB until now from September 2020.

The advisor **Massimo Stella** holds a PhD in **Complex Systems Simulations** and post-doc experience in **Data Science**. He is a founder of **Complex Science Consulting**, and a lecturer at the University of Exeter. Massimo does **psycholinguistics** and cognitive experiments in **change of mindsets** when people transfer from one knowledge area to another by **collaboration** or **individual choice making**. With Massimo, we did a psycholinguistic experiment and pitched it at TEDx Arendal, exhibition.

What people write to Wise Jester

A CEO of a blockchain-powered company in plastic waste recycling and owner of the Oslo Blockchain Cluster: *“If I want to go into this to find a fun collaboration or a collaborator who are anonymous, and to see who is qualified, it would be great to see a list of “secret projects” I did not know about and might become a part of. It would be interesting to join those networks, unknown, and anonymously be able to help someone and get rewarded somehow. Maybe I could find people from Google to join me, let say, for an hour per week, so I can get some advice.”*

A business strategy consultant & ecosystem facilitator, self-employed freelancer, collaborator at the Systems Innovation London Hub: *“Your work sounds fascinating, I like the sound of Wise Jester bringing AI to something I often contemplate as a problem – people being separated by hierarchies or indeed worldviews. I'm curious to see how it emerges.”*

An UX designer and consultant with international background: *“It is a really special project. It is really cool and really novel. It feels like you are very playful, and this project is very playful. I can see it attracting a certain type of people. That is usually how cool, innovative things work, right? It is not for the general public. It is like with the first smartphone. Weird nerds, technology nerds who were interested. I have an impression that the system will be interesting for very special companies: startups or freelancers, companies that are fed up with their recruitment systems...”*

<https://www.wisejester.org/>

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*Anna A. Zaytseva,
Founder of Wise Jester AS*